

Development of ethnic hair mimetic models for the evaluation of hair cosmetic treatments

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Hair, beyond its aesthetic significance, also holds considerable psychological and social importance, having historically served as a relevant marker of social status, culture, and identity (1). It is a complex system, composed of various morphological elements that work together to provide protective and thermal insulation functions. Hair fibers are essentially composed of dead, fully keratinized cells, organized into three main components – cuticle, cortex, and occasionally medulla – and exhibit a diversified chemical composition. This composition is predominantly made up of structural proteins, mainly keratin, complemented by lipids, water, pigments, and trace elements (2). Additionally, hair is generally classified into three major groups according to ethnic origin: Asian, African, and Caucasian, each presenting distinct structural and morphological characteristics (3). Given its relevance, numerous cosmetic products have been developed to cleanse, protect, color, enhance shine, or modify hair shape (4). During the development of new hair products, it is essential to assess their impact on hair fiber (5). Although hair fibers are widely used as models to evaluate the macroscopic effects of cosmetic formulations, assessing the permeation of their constituents into the inner regions of the fiber - particularly the cortex and medulla - remains limited, mainly due to the intrinsic structural complexity of the hair shaft (6). Nevertheless, analyzing this interaction is crucial for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying the structural and functional changes in hair induced by cosmetic formulations, as well as to improve their performance. The experimental work of my Master thesis aims to develop simple, reproducible, and representative hair mimetic models of different ethnic background, Caucasian, African and Asian, incorporating protein and lipidic fractions

taking into consideration the differences in composition of these types of hairs. These models are being fabricated by electrospinning, combining keratin and lipids extracted from hair of each ethnic group with poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA). After different curing methods and physicochemical characterization, including morphological analysis by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), chemical profiling by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), surface analysis by contact angle measurements and mechanical evaluation by tensile testing, providing insights into their elasticity, flexibility, and resistance to deformation, the models will be validated through permeation assays of cosmetic compounds and/or formulations using Franz diffusion cells.

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